

Multiple Interacting Collective Modes and Phonon Gap in Phospholipid Membranes

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Abstract

We combine Brillouin neutron scattering measurements with recent Inelastic X-ray Scattering¹ to propose a model for the collective dynamics of phospholipid bilayers. Neutron and X-ray spectra were fitted by the model response function associated to the Hamiltonian of an interacting-phonon system. This approach allows for a comprehensive and unprecedented picture of the vibrational collective features of phospholipids. At low wavevectors Q , the dispersion relations can be interpreted in terms of two acoustic-like modes, one longitudinal and one transverse, plus a dispersionless optic-like mode. The transverse mode of the liquid phase shows a phonon gap that can be linked to a passive transport mechanism through membranes, an interpretation that was proposed in Ref.¹. At higher Q s, the interaction of the longitudinal acoustic excitation with the dispersionless mode gives rise to a pattern that is consistent with avoided-crossing behavior. Evidence is found for a slow- to fast-sound transition, similarly to bulk water and other biomolecules

A consistent and comprehensive picture of the vibrational dynamics of phospholipid bilayers at THz frequencies is pivotal to frame their role in the membrane functionality. In particular, the density fluctuations of the hydrocarbon chains at the picosecond time scale are believed to be responsible for the increased membrane elasticity² and to influence the

transport of small molecules and ions across the bilayer³. While a vast literature on single-particle thermal motions of lipid membranes exists⁴⁻¹⁰, their collective dynamics started to receive attention lately. The first evidence for the existence of collective dynamics in lipid bilayers was reported by inelastic X-ray scattering (IXS) experiments¹¹⁻¹³. Consistently with molecular dynamics (MD) simulations¹⁴⁻¹⁶, a longitudinal acoustic-like mode was observed by IXS and attributed to the lateral collective motion of the lipid acyl chains. At small values of the in-plane wavevector transfer Q , a linear increase of the frequency, similarly to liquids, was found, which was, however, ensued by a non-trivial Q -dispersion, with a maximum at a certain Q value and a minimum at $Q_o \simeq 1.4 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$. This value, close to the first maximum of the static structure factor arising from interchain structural correlations, suggests that $Q_o/2$ can be interpreted as the limit of the pseudo-Brillouin zone of a two-dimensional liquid. The inelastic neutron scattering (INS) investigation of¹⁷ reported a minimum in the dispersion curve deeper in the gel than in the liquid phase and, as predicted by MD simulation¹⁴, the presence of an optic-like excitation at about 14 meV. More recently, a quite complex scenario for the collective dynamics of phospholipid bilayers was proposed by MD simulations¹⁸, which shows the presence of a transverse acoustic mode together with different optic-like modes up to 35 meV. The very recent IXS data¹ confirmed the presence of an additional acoustic mode and provided evidence for a *transverse phonon gap* in the liquid phase. As discussed in Refs.¹⁹⁻²², the phonon gap is, on a more general ground, a universal feature of disordered systems where a symmetry breaking, like for example the $SO(3)$, is caused by a symmetric anharmonic coupling. Consequently, the phonon gap is expected to appear also in the low temperature gel phase of the lipid membrane, although over a different energy and wave-vector region.

The scenario of the collective excitations in lipid bilayer is, therefore, far from being thoroughly understood. New and targeted experiments are mandatory to provide the best possible description of this complex landscape where dynamical coupling between different modes is expected, with a potential impact on biological functions of membrane.

Here, we report on the results of a novel and integrated approach of data analysis, where the data of a new Brillouin INS experiment and those of the recent IXS¹ measurement of coherent excitations of phospholipid bilayers are jointly analysed under the condition of being described *simultaneously by the same dynamical model*. By analysing INS and IXS data as a unique set, we provide straight evidence for the presence of at least three, mutually interacting, excitations, namely two acoustic and one optic mode. Further, the excitations coupling leads to avoided-crossing of the dispersion relations, and activates an energy transfer mechanism between the longitudinal-acoustic and the optic mode. Notably, the mode interaction revealed by the combined INS and IXS data analysis extends over a wide reciprocal space region, which likely plays a major role in the energy transfer processes in these biomolecules.

Neutron measurements were carried out on both the gel and liquid phases of 1,2-dimyristoyl-sn-glycero-3-phosphatidylcholine (DMPC) lipid bilayers, which are directly comparable with those of the DPPC bilayers investigated in Ref.¹. INS spectra were collected using the Brillouin neutron spectrometer BRISP²³ (Institut Laue-Langevin, Grenoble, France), to cover the energy and wavevector transfer region $-20 \text{ meV} \leq \hbar\omega \leq 20 \text{ meV}$ and $0.2 \text{ \AA}^{-1} \leq Q \leq 1.5 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$, at the two temperatures $T = 303 \text{ K}$, where the sample is in liquid crystalline (fluid, L_α) phase characterized by a high liquid-like disorder of the acyl chains⁷, and at 283 K , where the sample is in the highly ordered gel phase $L_{\beta'}$ ²⁴. Considering that the main transition temperatures in DMPC and DPPC are different¹, the choice of the temperature setting values for the neutron experiment was carefully made in order to stabilize DMPC in the same phase as DPPC. It is worth of note that possible differences between the DPPC and DMPC collective dynamics arising from the deuteration of the latter are neglected, even though the phase transition temperature of deuterated DMPC is shifted by about 4°C ⁷. However, as far as the low-frequency collective dynamics is considered, the influence of deuteration has been shown to be small in other biological systems such as proteins²⁵. The extended description of the neutron experiments and the details of sample preparation are provided

in the Supporting Information. Here we report the major steps of the experimental work and show, for comparison purpose with x-rays, only selected neutron spectra. This is to give more emphasis to the joint INS and IXS analysis and the discussion of the results. The sample, containing 36 mole of D₂O per lipid mole, was prepared according to the protocol of Ref.²⁶ to obtain aligned multilayers of DMPC-d54 on thin mica strips. In the model membrane DMPC-d54, 54 out of 72 hydrogen atoms of the acyl chains were substituted by deuterium atoms to enhance the coherent contribution to the INS cross section. The sample was composed of 250 layers with six 80 μm thick ¹⁰B spacers inserted to reduce multiple scattering. The sample holder was designed to preserve the correct alignment of the mica strips. The sample was then sealed in a properly shielded aluminum cell with a small water reservoir to maintain the hydration. A temperature stability better than 0.5 K was ensured to keep the sample in gel or liquid phase.

Due to the long-standing problem of attaining a 100% RH at the sample surface^{27,28}, we cannot be sure that fully hydration is attained. On the other hand this is not a primary issue for the present study. It may only be important that the amount of water is enough for gel-liquid transition to set in, when the temperature is raised.

The structure of the sample was controlled by deriving the static structure factor $S(Q, 0)$ from the data collected at the IN5 spectrometer (Institut Laue-Langevin, Grenoble, France), shown in Fig. 1 for gel and liquid phases of DMPC-d54. A sharp diffraction *elastic* peak, already ascribed to the correlations of pairs of adjacent hydrocarbon chains in the lipid bilayer¹⁷, was observed at $Q = 1.49 \pm 0.02 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$ in the gel and $Q = 1.41 \pm 0.02 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$ in the liquid phase. We note that the first diffraction peak of hydration water²⁹, which occurs at about $Q=2.0 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$ in bulk water, here was not detected. This indicates a rather disordered structure of water molecules in DMPC-d54 in comparison with bulk water, as already observed by X-rays¹¹. The much larger coherent elastic signal of the lipid phase compared to water indicates that also the inelastic features stem mainly from DMPC modes (see also SI).

The dynamic structure factors $S^{exp}(Q, \hbar\omega)$ at $Q = 0.974 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$ are plotted in Fig. 2. The

Figure 1: (color online). Static structure factor $S(Q, 0)$ of DMPC-d54 at $T = 283$ K (gel phase, blue dots) and $T = 303$ K (liquid phase, red circles). The widths W_p are shown by horizontal bars. Full lines are guides to the eye.

IXS data¹ at the same Q -value are also shown for the sample in the two phases. Coupling INS-IXS data enables to effectively exploit complementary characteristics of the two probes and techniques, namely: i) the INS resolution function is well described by a Gaussian while the IXS resolution function is characterized by extended wings that can mask the weak inelastic structures, ii) IXS measurements do not suffer the dynamics range limitations present in INS, iii) INS on deuterated samples is sensitive to deuterium atoms in addition to heavy atoms, while IXS is dominated by C and P atoms, in the lipid, with H atoms being almost invisible.

Therefore, the combined analysis of INS and IXS is a powerful approach to study the collective dynamics in disordered media as more complex models can be applied to describe the system. The readiness of one *same* vibrational model that, once convoluted with the different energy resolution functions, is able to optimally describe INS and IXS experiments, provides an accurate unprecedented picture of the collective dynamics of the system.

To properly address modeling of $S^{exp}(Q, \hbar\omega)$, we considered the results of recent far-

IR experiments³⁰ and MD simulation¹⁸ reporting inelastic spectral features well visible at about 6 meV, 11 meV and 14 meV, which suggests the presence of a multi-component low-frequency vibrational landscape. Therefore, we adopted a model consisting of an elastic line plus a phonon-like contribution based on the Hamiltonian $\mathcal{H} = \mathcal{H}_o + \mathcal{H}_{damp} + \mathcal{H}_{int}$. Here $\mathcal{H}_o = 1/2 \sum_{\mathbf{Q}_j} [P_{\mathbf{Q}_j}^\dagger P_{\mathbf{Q}_j} + \omega_{\mathbf{Q}_j}^2 Q_{\mathbf{Q}_j}^\dagger Q_{\mathbf{Q}_j}]$ describes the system of N harmonic oscillators with $Q_{\mathbf{Q}_j}$, $P_{\mathbf{Q}_j}$ and $\hbar\omega_{\mathbf{Q}_j}$ respectively coordinates, momenta, and *bare energies* of the non-interacting system. The term \mathcal{H}_{damp} describes the mode damping due to disorder and/or anharmonic interactions. The last term $\mathcal{H}_{int} = 1/2 \sum_{\mathbf{Q}_{jj'}} [U_{jj'}(\mathbf{Q}) Q_{\mathbf{Q}_j}^\dagger Q_{\mathbf{Q}_{j'}} + hc]$ accounts for mode interaction. When the interaction term \mathcal{H}_{int} is negligible, the dynamic structure factor reduces to $S_{DHO}(Q, \hbar\omega)$, i.e. the usual model of N damped harmonic oscillators (DHOs) plus the elastic contribution. In DMPC-d54 the interaction term \mathcal{H}_{int} cannot be neglected: indeed, all the modes experimentally observed do not belong to orthogonal symmetries and do have a component of longitudinal symmetry as the only visible by INS and IXS. This is a clear signature of mode interaction. The most appropriate model to describe the collective dynamics of this system is therefore the interacting phonon model. We recall that such a model was successfully applied to systems like glassy SiSe₂³¹ and liquid Zn³², where only two modes were sufficient to describe the experimental spectra.

The dynamic structure factor associated to the full Hamiltonian \mathcal{H} , with the interaction $U_{jj'}(Q)$ switched on, is

$$\begin{aligned}
S^{mod}(Q, \hbar\omega) = & A_e(Q) \delta(\hbar\omega) + \\
& + [n(\hbar\omega) + 1] \sum_{\mathbf{Q}_{jj'}} A_{jj'}(Q) S_{jj'}(Q, \hbar\omega)
\end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

where $n(\hbar\omega)$ is the Bose factor and $A_e(Q)$ and $A_{jj'}(Q)$ are probe-dependent amplitudes. $S_{jj'}(Q, \hbar\omega)$ are the mode-mode dynamic structure factors, related to the Fourier transform of $\langle Q_{\mathbf{Q}_{j'}}^\dagger(0) Q_{\mathbf{Q}_j}(t) \rangle$, which, using the equation of motion³³, are given by the jj' element of the matrix $\{\delta_{jj'}[\omega^2 - \omega_{\mathbf{Q}_j}^2 - \Sigma_j(Q, \omega)] + U_{jj'}(Q)\}^{-1}$, with $\Sigma_j(Q, \omega) \simeq i\Gamma_j(Q) \omega$ the self-energy

associated to \mathcal{H}_{damp} .

A simple and physically sound assumption was that the *in-plane* dynamic structure factor does not depend on the \mathbf{Q} in-plane direction, as the DMPC-d54 sample consisted of several layers not coherently oriented. Also, we assumed that only the diagonal terms $S_{jj}(Q, \hbar\omega)$ contribute. The model response function $S^{mod}(Q, \hbar\omega)$ produced a good and stable fit of all the INS and IXS data with the choice $N = 3$, that is for a number of modes equal to 3. The free parameters of the fit were the dynamic variables ω_{Qj} , $\Gamma_j(Q)$ and $U_{jj'}(Q)$, with the same values for both INS and IXS, while the amplitudes $A(Q)$ were obviously different for the two probes. The excellent results of the fit are shown in Fig.2, where the individual components $j = 1, 2, 3$ are also plotted. We observe that the more structured profile of $S_{jj}(Q, \hbar\omega)$ functions compared with the simpler shape of the $S_{DHO}(Q, \hbar\omega)$, is a necessary ingredient for the accuracy of the fit.

Figure 2: (color online). Experimental $S^{exp}(Q, \hbar\omega)$ (dots) versus energy at $Q = 0.974 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$. The best fit $S^{mod}(Q, \hbar\omega)$ is shown (full line) together with the longitudinal $j = 1$ component (short-dashed line), the low energy $j = 2$ excitation (thin line) and the optic-like $j = 3$ mode (long-dashed line). The results for other Q values are reported in SM.

Insofar as the *bare energies* $\hbar\omega_j(Q)$ of the non-interacting system are provided by the fit with $S^{mod}(Q, \hbar\omega)$ (Eq.1) as the free fitting parameters, the *dressed* energies $\hbar\tilde{\omega}_j(Q)$ that represent the effective collective excitations of the system with the mode interactions accounted

Figure 3: (color online). Dispersion curves of interacting collective modes, i.e. *dressed* excitation energies, in lipid bilayers as obtained from Eq. 2 (full lines). *Bare* excitation energies, i.e. the free parameters of the fit by Eq. 1, are shown for $j = 1$ (squares), $j = 2$ (lozenges) and $j = 3$ (circles) modes (errors are within the symbol size). Dotted lines are interpolated curves to guide the eye through the *bare* modes. The dashed lines c_0 are obtained by taking the slopes of the $j =$ bare modes for gel and liquid phases. The $1 \leftrightarrow 3$ mode interaction is marked.

for, are obtained as the poles of the dynamic structure factor and calculated from the secular equation, i.e.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & (\omega^2 - \omega_{Q1}^2)(\omega^2 - \omega_{Q2}^2)(\omega^2 - \omega_{Q3}^2) + \\
 & -U_{12}^2(Q)(\omega^2 - \omega_{Q3}^2) - U_{13}^2(Q)(\omega^2 - \omega_{Q2}^2) = 0
 \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

in the limit $\Gamma_j(Q) \rightarrow 0^+$ and $j = 1, 2, 3$.

A first guess on the character of the interacting modes comes from the analysis of the dispersion curves of the *bare* excitations. With the help of the *bare* data, the pristine nature of the *dressed* mode as resulting from the intensity transfer due to mode-mode interaction, can be traced back. The energy dispersion for *bare* and *dressed* collective modes is shown in Fig.3 for gel and liquid phases.

As to the *bare* modes, at low- Q s the linearly dispersive mode, identified by $j = 1$, describes the propagation of longitudinal sound with an associated velocity $c_0 = 2330 \pm 200$ m/s in the gel phase and $c_0 = 1810 \pm 200$ m/s in the liquid phase. These extrapolated-to-zero values are in fair agreement with those from IXS¹¹ and Brillouin light scattering³⁴. The optic-like

mode, identified by $j = 3$, takes an energy value $\hbar\omega = 13 \pm 2$ meV when extrapolated to zero, and shows a weak temperature dependence with a softening at high Q . It can be related to the two optical branches with energies peaked at 12 meV and 15 meV, as obtained by MD simulations¹⁸, and the band at 14 meV, as measured by FTIR³⁰ and INS¹⁷, assigned to C–CH₃ translational dynamics³⁰. The dispersion of the low-energy mode, identified by $j = 2$, does not depend on temperature and can be related to a transverse acoustic branch. The lack of data at low- Q does not allow for an accurate determination of the velocity that, once extrapolated, takes the value 1770 ± 400 m/s, larger than what obtained in¹ from the analysis of the IXS data by a double-DHO model.

The *dressed* modes plotted with continuous lines in Fig.3 are the three solutions $\hbar\tilde{\omega}_j(Q)$ of the secular equation (Eq. 2), with their low- Q trend obtained by a smooth extrapolation to $Q = 0$ of the *bare* frequencies. A signature of the *dressed* energies, which is revealed in Fig.3, is the avoided-crossing between the longitudinal acoustic branch ($j = 1$) and the optic-like ($j = 3$) mode over the dynamic range 0.6 \AA^{-1} to 12 meV. We remark that this key feature became apparent thanks to the combined use of the two INS and IXS sets of data and partly to the more extended INS experimental range. The mode-mode interaction underlying the avoided-crossing implies an oscillator strength transfer between the two modes ($j = 1$ and $j = 3$), with the consequent exchange and mixture of their character. This is why the high-energy mode at $Q \geq 0.8 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$ can be attributed to longitudinal fluctuations, with an associated high-frequency velocity $c_\infty = 3330 \pm 150 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ in gel and $c_\infty = 3490 \pm 150 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ in liquid phase. Also we note that such a high-energy mode was not visible in previous experiments, probably because of limitations arising from either broad resolution or limited dynamic range which are removed by the present coupled analysis of INS and IXS data.

Notably, the high-energy mode propagates with a velocity similar to that observed for an excitation with the same longitudinal character in *dry* proteins²⁵, DNA and chromatin³⁵, hydration water of biomolecules^{36,37} and bulk water^{38–40}. Also akin to these systems is the strong increase of the longitudinal ($j = 1$) mode velocity from the low- Q values ($c_0 \sim 2000$

m/s discussed above) up to c_∞ . Such a characteristic behavior, also referred to as *slow- to fast-sound transition* and originally considered as an anomalous characteristic of water^{29,38–40}, here observed, can then be safely extended to the case of membranes. These similarities lead us to speculate that the fast mode could play a key role for the dynamical coupling at the biomolecule-solvent and biomolecule-biomolecule interface.

An equally interesting behavior is shown by the low-lying ($j = 2$) mode that takes real values of energy only at $Q \geq 0.3 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$ in gel and 0.6 \AA^{-1} in liquid phase. This particular result is in close relation with the existence of a *phononic gap* introduced by the disorder, as discussed in¹, which is here described as a *temperature-dependent* mode interaction. As already mentioned and thoroughly discussed in Refs.^{19–22}, the phonon gap is a characteristic feature of disordered systems where symmetry breaking in phonon excitations appears. As such, it is system-independent. Indeed, for the lipid membrane the gap is observed in the liquid phase¹ and its presence suggested in the gel phase by the low Q data shown in Fig.3. A direct and complete characterization of the phonon gap in the gel phase is, however, limited by the minimum useful Q value that is accessible by both INS and IXS experiments. The coupled analysis of two independent INS and IXS data sets gives a more solid experimental ground to the interpretation of the origin of the transverse phonon gap. We note that the peculiar dispersion of the $j = 2$ mode is straightly obtained from the present data analysis without resorting to the use of the intensity of the rather weak low-energy mode, which is also very close to the strong elastic peak¹. The trend of this branch firmly confirms that in the fluid phase the phonon gap prevents the low-energy modes to propagate over a significant distance, a behaviour that has been linked to the formation of local short-lived and nanometer-sized lipid clusters, which in turn underlie the mechanisms of passive transport in membranes¹. In this respect, the width W_p of the diffraction peak in the gel phase is resolution-limited (Fig.1), thus suggesting an average size of the domains over which lipid tails are coordinated in excess of $2\pi/W_p \sim 3 \text{ nm}$. Considering the size of the ordered regions as the maximum distance d over which the low energy mode can propagate, we can use a

critical wave-vector $Q_c = 2\pi/d$ as the cut-off value at which the phonon gap appears. With $d \simeq 3$ nm, it follows $Q_c \simeq 0.2 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$ as also suggested by Fig. 3. On the other hand, in the liquid phase $d \simeq 2$ nm, while the size of the ordered regions as estimated by the Q_c cut-off in Fig. 3 is $d = 2\pi/Q_c \simeq 1$ nm. After extrapolating to $Q \rightarrow 0$ the $j = 2$ branch, we get for this mode a sound velocity of $(1050 \pm 200 \text{ m/s})$. We assign to this low-energy branch a transverse-like character, due to the similarity of the sound speed value with those found for the DMPC gel phase by MD simulation¹⁸ and Brillouin light scattering measurements³⁴ of respectively the transverse and the off-plane acoustic mode.

As to the damping factors, it is worth to note that a modest temperature dependence is observed (see SM). The $\Gamma_j(Q)$ for the longitudinal $j = 1$ mode has a Q -squared dependence already observed in dry proteins²⁵ and protein hydration water³⁶ other than DNA³⁷, that is related to the presence of different intramolecular localized modes.

The present results offer a novel picture for the collective dynamics of lipid bilayers. Using a three-mode interaction model, the overall dynamics, as determined in INS and IXS experiments, is coherently described. This new observation demonstrates the existence of a third mode over the present energy window. Assuming the modes observed in Ref.¹ lie in plane, the third mode is expected to produce *transverse density fluctuations* with respect to the membrane surface, as the three eigenmodes we found cannot be coplanar. As the dynamic structure factor measured by INS and IXS is proportional to the *longitudinal density fluctuations*, a purely off-plane fluctuation is not directly visible. However, mode interaction causes a mixing of modes and hence a change of the eigenvector in addition to that of frequencies. A similarly quite complex dynamic behavior has been recently observed in liquid crystals that are able to sustain both acoustic and optical phonon excitations propagating down to the nanoscale, also thanks to the prepared quasi-Gaussian resolution function⁴¹. The experimental findings, other than this general observation, show the existence of avoided-crossing of the longitudinal acoustic branch ($j = 1$) with an optic-like mode ($j = 3$), as already discussed in the case of glycine⁴² and ribonuclease⁴³. We observe that the mode-mode inter-

action, producing evident avoided crossing and affecting transport properties of the system, was reported also in thermoelectric materials⁴⁴, which suggests the effect to be present in a variety of complex systems. Additionally, our analysis revealed a similarity of the longitudinal mode velocity c_∞ in lipid membranes with other biological systems, and water as well, an effect which is going to appear as a universal feature of the elastic behavior of many biological systems. This is a quite multifaceted scenario, compared to the one where the THz collective spectrum can be mainly assigned to a single acoustic mode^{11,17}. When structural disorder and finite lifetime give rise to broad overdamped inelastic features, the collective dynamics of complex systems can be interpreted only by using complementary experimental and theoretical approaches. Finally, we mention also that the present description provides strong support to the speculative conclusion from recent IXS investigations¹ by which phonon-like excitations induce and/or mediate the formation of water wires inside dynamic defects in lipid membranes, thus giving rise to anomalously high proton permeability.

Supporting Information Detailed description of the neutron experiments, details of the sample preparation and the modeling approach.

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